

Laboratory Workstation to Prepare Students for Industrial Application of Electric Drives

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Abstract

This paper presents the development of workstations to be used in the laboratory component of a course on electric drives for electro-mechanical engineering technology (EMET) students at the Pennsylvania State University, Altoona College. The goal is to provide students a hands-on experience with the operation and application of industrial electric drives. This approach better supports ABET criterion for curriculum content, which states that engineering technology program curriculum must **focus on the applied aspects of engineering science and engineering**.

Requirements

- Students will learn to use and apply industrial electric drives
- Lab assignments will demonstrate how theories from lecture are applied in practice
- Exercises contribute to skills in communication, teamwork, and experimentation
- Activities should be interesting to students to stimulate academic curiosity
- Laboratories should culminate in a project, possibly in collaboration with a concurrent course on mechanical drives.
- low cost

Hardware Implementation and Experiments

Motor Generator Set:

- Load is a DC machine (250 Watt, 42V, 6A)
- Motor under test: DC, BLDC, and Induction motors
- 1000 line encoder feedback + Hall sensor (for BLDC)

Host Computer User Interface: Driveware is available at no cost from AMC to provide a computer interface

- Allows setup, configuration, tuning, troubleshooting, and monitoring the motor controller
- Provides virtual oscilloscope and meters to view phase current/voltages, DC bus current/voltage, speed, position, and more
- Supports management of user-specified motion profiles at the drive level

Industrial Drives:

- **Load control** is a current control PWM drive with regenerative capability. 8A, 20-80VDC rating
- Interface PCB required to mount the drive and provide convenient access to signals
- **Motor Under Test controller** must be able to control DC, BLDC, IM, and Stepper motors
- Digiflex® model DPRALTE 020B080 from Advanced Motion Controls
- Signal interface board is required to provide access to signals, and measurement of voltages/currents in standalone mode

Lab Exercises:

1. Driveware and lab hardware familiarization
2. PWM H-bridge operation, 3-phase inverter
3. DC Motor/Load parameter determination and load testing
4. Torque and speed control of DC machine
5. Position control and motion control basics (homing, indexing, user-defined motion profiles etc.)
6. BLDC motor operation (Hall Sensor only commutation) and parameter determination. Torque and speed control and load testing
7. PMSM motor operation, torque, speed, and position control
8. Induction motor parameter determination, tuning, and operation in vector control mode
9. Stepper motor operation
10. Final project in collaboration with concurrent course in Mechanical Drives

Results and Conclusions

The new laboratory workstations using industrial electric drives have been fully deployed in the Spring of 2025. As confirmed in a student survey, students feel that they are being well-prepared for industrial practice in the operation, application, and troubleshooting of electric motors and drives, and that the lab exercises support understanding of lecture material

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	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
The lab component of Electric Drives is preparing you for industry practice, including application, operation, and troubleshooting of industrial electric motor drives	0	0	0	12	6
The laboratory component of Electric Drives helps to enforce topics and theories discussed in lecture	0	0	0	10	8